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Ubale Amol Baban

[Editorial/Head Office: 108, Gokuldham Society, Dr.Ambedkar chowk, Near
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**DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF E-CONTENT ON PHYSICAL FEATURE OF
INDIA**

Education subject

Aditya Prakash Rao

Vinita Rao.

Abstract

In modern world of education teaching and learning become digital. It makes education more convenient and interesting. An electronic content or e-content is demand of current education system .E-content is a digital content that can be transferred over a computerized devices or computer network. It helps in the easy and effective learning. Sample 50 students were taken it was divided in to experimental group and non experimental group. Non experimental group taught by traditional method and experimental group taught by using the E-Content .It is found that achievement of experimental group is better than non experimental group.

Key word: *e-content, physical features*

Introduction

Educationists around the world are striving to make learning more accessible, realistic and relevant to the learners. The change in education system is aimed to increase the rate of learner's response towards learning. Earlier, Educationist its World Wide Web and the potentiality of the computer network that is drastically changing education system.

Educationist derived the idea of radio, then films and television, to impart educational information, all of which were the era of paradigm of change in education system today. So, in such phenomena online instructional resources are gaining more and more popularity in educational System E-content is one of most preferred ways and means of delivering content at the convenience of learners. E-learning is a new method of teaching and learning that is developed based on the desire and need of the modern society. Although, the function of content is similar to the hard text, the approaches and pedagogies are encouraging and interesting in E-content.

India is an ancient country, known as Bhartvarsh. It covers an area of 32,87,2631 sq. km. Lying entirely in the northern hemisphere the mainland extends measures 3214 km from north south between extreme latitudes and about 2933 km from east to west between extreme longitudes. It has a land frontier of about 15200 km. The country lies between 8°4' and 37°6' north of the Equator and is surrounded by the Bay of Bengal in the east, the Arabian Sea in the west and the Indian Ocean to the south. The total length of the coastline of the mainland, Lakswadeep group of islands and Andaman and Nicobar group of islands is 7,516.5 km.

The physical features of India can be grouped under the following physiographic divisions:

- The Himalayan mountains
- The Northern Plains
- The Peninsular Plateau
- The Indian Desert
- The Coastal Plains
- The Islands

Prakashe (2009) conducted a study on “Managing e-Content; Ways and Issues” with the aim to learn its effectiveness and efficiency in teaching and learning. However, the study revealed that there were several issues encountered while making attempt to digitize e-Content. It is suggested to make every endeavor to promote e-Content for the benefit of learners and other beneficiaries. . Linda (2009) pointed out that E-content reduces the time hugely by allowing teachers to easily share their course curriculums online. It also showed that as a result of e-content, many experience dramatic increase in performance by the school goers as well as distance learners.

Clark and Bilham (2008) conducted study on Shillong Plateau related to Miocene rise of the Shillong Plateau and its origin. It also describes the beginning of the Eastern Himalaya and its end in form of current Shillong Plateau. It reflects type of vegetation present in this Plateau.

Itamar et al. (2008) in study entitled “Do E-learning Technologies improve the effectiveness and efficiency of E-learning technologies in education. It was revealed that adopting and applying new e-learning methods and techniques generates a role-transition, turning lectures from knowledge-provider into mentors. Enriching the curricula with learning-based courses improves efficiency, without reducing academic effectiveness at the verge of transforming educational system. Bastia (2006) conducted study on Indian sedimentary basins with special focus on emerging east coast deepwater frontiers. It describes sedimentary basin of coastal region and the effect of global warming on these coastal regions that causes rapid change in geological status of coastal region.

Verma and Sharma (2005) studied on the uses computer as a device of teaching and found that tele-teachers, tele-educational material Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) has developed into a powerful, flexible and increasingly effective tool of education. The statement strongly supports the electronic modes of education, which stresses to e-learning, and are more effective, realistic and learner-centered. Omwenga et. al (2005) held a discussion on structuring E-content development framework using a Stratified objectives-driven methodology. The discussion was aimed at promoting content development using framed objectives as a guiding philosophy for structuring E-content. Discussion pointed out that content development plays a key role in E-learning and that, it requires expert knowledge in the subject area, patience in creating the necessary objects that make up quality, interactive courseware, and a high sense of creativity in structuring and sequencing the topics to make a complete whole.

After having examined a number of studies carried out by different personals and different reports propounded by various organization and individuals on electronic content and electronic learning, it can be concluded that electronic materials have greater impact on learning in higher education.

Significance of the research The learning material developed through E-Content makes the students curios and motivating. It also support discipline and give better academic results.

Statement of the research The present study is aimed at development of electronic learning objects and the evaluation of same content to find out its effectiveness, so the problem is stated as *Development and Evaluation of E-content on Physical Features of India*.

Objectives of the research To develop E-Content on the topics-

1. The physical features of India.
2. To assess the effectiveness of developed e-content.

Hypothesis of the research There exist significant difference in the achievement of control group and experimental group.

Delimitations of the research

- The study is delimited to the topic Development and evaluation of e-content on Physical Features of India.
- The study is delimited to module The Himalayan Mountains and The Northern Plain.
- The study is delimited to Kendriya Vidyalaya of Jalandhar in Punjab.
- The study is delimited to CBSE School.
- The study is delimited to 9th class.

The study is delimited to 50 students divide in 2 groups of each 25 students.

PLAN AND PROCEDURE

Method : The present study was carried out applying *experimental method*

Sampling: A purposive sample is a non-representative subset of some larger population, and is constructed to serve a very specific need or purpose. Based on the above procedure data were collected from 25 users of E-content material and 25 subjects to whom classroom teaching was done (group-B) through conventional method. The effectiveness of the content developed was compared with the (group-A) who learned through normal classroom teaching. Thus, randomized group pre-test and post-test design was applied for determining the efficacy of the material developed. An achievement test to measure effectiveness of E-content was administered after teaching the lesson through two different methods (i.e. conventional and experimental method).

TOOLS FOR DEVELOPING E-CONTENT

Three type of tools used

(A)Softwares (B)Equipments (C)Questionnaire

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

(1)Mean (2) SD (3) T-test

RESULT:

The Standard Deviation of controlled group was 21.8 while experimental group was 8.67. The computed t-value being 6.42 has been found to be significant at both the confident levels of confidence i.e. 0.05 and 0.01 indicating that there exists significant difference in the achievement of controlled group and experimental group on post-test. The hypothesis of the present study which stated that there exists significant difference in the achievement of controlled group and experimental group on post test stands accepted.

DISCUSSION: The two groups were formed on the basis of the previous achievement and later the group validation was done through pre-test, which demonstrated the equivalent achievement level of the two groups as the two groups were found to be having no significant differences. There after the controlled group and experimental group were designated. The post-test results for both groups were analyzed and found the existence of statistically significant differences between experimental group and controlled group. Thus, the hypothesis, “there exist significant difference between and controlled and experimental group” of the study is accepted.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS:

- E-content offers a new mode of engagement with ideas via both material and social interactivity online.
- Socially, e-content helps to reduce social differences by offering greater responsibility for individualized learning.
- Practically, e-content offers the ability to manage quality at scale, and share resources across networks, its greater flexibilities of provision in time and place makes it good for widening participation.

- It assist teacher in identification of Individual differences.

CONCLUSIONS

- The developed E-content on Physical Features of India Illustrates different ranges of Himalaya and Sub division of Northern Plains. Himalaya mountain ranges and Northern Plains were filmed in the form of audio-visual by adding animations that could be used as an instructional tool by students and other teaching professionals.
- To know the effectiveness of the developed e-content on the topic Physical features of India. The controlled group was taught through conventional method and experimental group taught with the help of e-content. Post-test was taken on both the groups and on the basis of the results following conclusion has been drawn:
- Students who were treated through E-content answered more questions correctly in the post-test than students who were taught with conventional method. So this can be concluded that there exists significant difference in the achievement of control group and experimental group. Achievement of students who are taught with e-content is higher than the students who are taught without e-content. This reflected the positive impact of the e-content. Hence hypothesis is accepted.

LIMITATIONS

- For deep study it requires more time.
- Technical experts are required.
- It is quite expensive
- Lack of technical knowledge and
- Optimum of technical terms and terminologies could not be made.

SUGGESTIONS

- Development and evaluation of E-content on other disciplines.
- Effectiveness of E-content in relation to learner's attitude.
- Public views and opinions on E-content.
- Social attitude towards E-content.

- Online evaluation of E-content.
- E-content in relation to E-learning.
- Comparative study of E-content and Web Based Instruction.
- Computer Assisted Instruction versus E-content.
- Effectiveness of E-content in business and other organizations.
- Evaluation of e-content on Collaborative Learning.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Quality of content should be improved.
- E-content may be developed for all the disciplines.
- Seek more views of experts in relation to the particular discipline.
- Sample size for evaluation of the effectiveness of e-content should be increased to as many as possible.
- Qualitative and quantitative study should be emphasized to increase the significance of the study.
- Consideration may be taken for designing e-content to learner accessibility.

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